

VARIOUS ASPECTS OF CURRICULUM AND QUALITY OF EXECUTED PROGRAMME IN RURAL AND URBAN
PRESCHOOLS IN PARBHANI DISTRICT

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Abstract

A stratified random sample of 80 preschools were selected from rural area (40 Anganwadis) from 7 villages and remaining 40 preschools were selected from local Parbhani city, Marathwada region Maharashtra state. The data was collected by personally interviewing urban and rural preschool teachers, staff or Principal of the selected preschool, based on prepared checklist and observation. Results indicated that hundred per cent of rural children work with freedom under supervision and flexibility in programme with few activities. However urban preschools were providing variety of experiences to children through various activities. Higher percentage of urban preschools were following play-oriented programme (87.50%), informal teaching of 3R's (80.00%), use of teaching aids for various activities (85.00%), teachers change the place as per activity (85.00%). The corresponding values for rural preschools were 47.50, 62.50 and 62.50 percent respectively. The rural preschool teachers expressed that lot of time is spared in writing various reports & maintaining records and other activities. However, the percentage of urban preschools conducting these activities was seen to some extent (42.50 - 85%). Overall, it can be said that majority of the activities found to be conducted in urban preschools as compared to rural preschools.

Keywords: Curriculum, Preschool programme, Development, Early childhood education

Introduction

Early childhood education is a special branch of education that relates to the teaching of children from birth to six years of age (Mathur 2018). In terms of child's life, Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) is the period from birth to eight years of age (Malvankar 2018). It aims at the holistic development of a child's social, emotional, cognitive and physical needs in order to build a social and broad foundation for lifelong learning and wellbeing. A study by Gibbs (2012) showed low level of readiness in children for primary schools due to low quality of early childhood education. The quality of early childhood education relies on teachers efforts to provide education and care in line with the curriculum. Thus, curriculum implementation improves the quality of early childhood education (Chopra 2012).

Intervention was provided through various stimulatory activities, warm social interactions, play material, physical amenities and supportive nutrition (2-3 times in a week) for giving quality child care and education, for attaining their wholesome development. After six months, post test results revealed that intervention provided to young children brought about significant improvement in all the domains of development. Thus the efficacy of intervention programme proved to be effective not only in optimizing motor, mental, language and socio emotional development of young children but highly significant improvement was observed in home environment too (Bhalerao et al. 2009).

It was recommended that County government in collaboration with other stakeholders in early childhood, should come up with model preschools in informal set up to create conducive learning environments. It was stressed that there was also a need for frequent inspection of preschools to ensure safety and security standards to be observed and implemented (Mwoma et al (2018). A significant and positive relationship between parental involvement in the schooling of their children's academic achievement Parent-teacher conferences and parent-teacher face-to-face contact were perceived to be the most natured and desirable system of communication that improved not only childrens school outcomes but also discipline, attitude and attendance rates (Kimaro and Machumu 2015). Play materials should be safe and suitable to the child's age, abilities, and interests. Many advertisements lead consumers to think that play materials are better if they are expensive, store-bought items. The best play materials was selected based on their appropriateness for a child's age, development, and interests.(Rozario et al. 2018). In view of these

findings, the research was taken up to study various aspects of curriculum and quality of executed programme in rural and urban preschools in Parbhani dist. of Marathwada region, Maharashtra state.

Materials and Methods

A stratified random sample of 80 preschools were selected from rural area (40 Anganwadis) from total 7 villages, namely Pandhri, Nandapur, Takali, Daithna, Zari, Pingli and Bori. The remaining 40 preschools were selected from local Parbhani city of Marathwada region Maharashtra state. Prior to the study, the permission was obtained from the concerned organizer/ head/ teacher of the preschool, for collecting information regarding their preschool. The data pertaining to the study was collected by personally interviewing urban and rural preschool teachers, staff or Principal of the selected preschool, based on prepared checklist and observation. The data collected was pooled, tabulated and discussed.

Z test

'Z' test was applied to compare the percentages of the various responses to the different parameters with regard to the urban and rural preschools, as per the standard procedure given by Sharma, 2005.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 exhibit various aspects of curriculum followed in selected rural and urban preschools. It was seen that irrespective of area, both rural as well as urban preschools (100%) were following balance in individual and group activities as well as guided and free activities. While urban preschools surpassed the counterparts in following the balance between indoor and outdoor activities, vigorous & quite activities. Similarly all urban preschools were proceeding their programme from simple to complex, familiar to unfamiliar activities and easy to difficult tasks (100%).

It is obvious from the table that, almost all preschools followed the guidelines of NCERT (2018), for the hours of preschool, staff spending their time for preparation of activities, organizing parents meeting, use of mother tongue in preschool, activities promoting social, emotional, speech & language development of children. These findings are in line with Desetty et al. (1998). However rural preschools were found conducting relatively less activities, for fostering large and fine muscle development (52.50%), intellectual development (55.00%), moral development (30.00%), creativity (67.50%) as well as activities as per developmental level of children, age, interest and need of children (35.00%). In addition, for the parameters like activities to be conducted in a day was observed to be comparatively less in rural than urban

preschools (40%). It is clear that hundred percent rural children work with freedom under supervision and flexibility in programme with few activities. However urban preschools were providing variety of experiences to children through various activities, the children work with freedom under teachers supervision with multi sensorial learning experiences, teachers give first hand or manipulative experiences to children, conduct child centered programme taking into consideration their age & developmental level, followed flexibility in programme and almost all programme were found to imbibe cleanliness, independence, discipline, confidence among preschoolers. The corresponding percentages for the rural preschools were 72.50, 100, 42.50, 45, 47.50 percent respectively. Relatively a higher percentage of urban preschools were following play oriented programme (87.50%), informal teaching of 3R's (80.00%), use of teaching aids for various activities (85.00%), teachers change the place as per activity (85.00%). The corresponding values for rural preschools were 47.50, 62.50 and 62.50 percent respectively.

The highly significant differences were noted in rural and urban preschools with regard to various aspects of curriculum followed in selected preschools. Overall it can be inferred that urban preschools were following most of the aspects of curriculum programme when compared to rural preschools. Majority of the preschools from rural as well as urban area were found to adopt informal method of evaluation like daily observation of children while performing various activities, reading, writing and through games. These findings are line with (Mwoma *et al.* 2018) and (Roul *et al.* 2012).

Table 2 describe the various activities conducted in selected rural and urban preschools. It was observed that all rural preschool teachers were conducting indoor play, songs activity. They were also providing snacks like lapshi (kheer), khichadi, green peas usal as per government supply. While in urban preschools; prayer, outdoor play, readiness activity like 3R's, indoor play, snacks, songs and creative activity were conducted in almost all preschools (100%) very regularly. The other enlisted activities like outdoor play, readiness activity, science activity or creative activity were not seen to be conducted in rural preschools. The rural preschool teachers expressed that lot of time is spared in writing various reports & maintaining records and other activities like home visits, distribution of supplementary food, survey of pregnant women etc which affect their involvement in conducting childrens activities. However the percentage of urban preschools conducting these activities was seen to some extent (42.50 - 85%) with highly significant differences. These findings are line with NCERT, (2015). These preschool teachers were monitored by the supervisors for various activities they conduct in preschool. Still it can be said that majority of the activities were conducted in urban preschools as compared to rural preschools.

Table 4.3 reveals qualitative parameters of available outdoor play equipments and materials in selected rural and urban preschools. It was found that very few outdoor equipments and materials were available in rural preschools but the almost all available equipments and material were safe, durable, colourful, attractive, light in weight and having good quality. But it was found that majority of the rural preschools placed swings and slides in classroom itself, being it was portable. Although it was not properly installed from childrens' point of view for their easy movements and there were chances for collision of children. But it was observed that children were enjoying it. While in urban preschools it was noticed that, majority of the criteria for good quality of outdoor equipments and materials were fulfilled as safe, durable, attractive, light in weight, cost effective, proper installation of equipment, appropriate size and appropriate in number for childrens availability and proper maintenance. Some of these findings are in support of the results recorded by (Rozario *et al.* 2018).

Conclusion

It is obvious from the result almost all preschools followed the guidelines of NCERT (2018), including the hours of preschool, staff spending their time for preparation of activities, organizing parents meeting, use of mother tongue in preschool, activities were found to be promoting social, emotional, speech & language development of children. Majority of the preschools from rural as well as urban area were found to adopt informal method of evaluation like daily observation of children while performing various activities as reading, writing and through games. The highly significant differences were noted in rural and urban preschools with regard to various aspects of curriculum followed in selected preschools. Almost all available equipments and material were safe, durable, colourful, attractive, light in weight and having good quality in rural and urban preschools. Overall, it can be inferred that urban preschools were following most of the aspects of curriculum programme when compared to rural preschools.

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Fig 2: Various activities conducted in selected rural and urban preschools

Fig 3: Qualitative parameters of available outdoor play equipment's & material in selected rural and urban preschools

Table 1: Various aspects of curriculum followed in selected rural and urban preschools

Aspects of curriculum	Percentages of preschools based on area (n-80)		Z values
	Rural (40)	Urban (40)	
Balance in activities			
Individual & group	40 (100.00)	40 (100.00)	NS
Guided & free	40 (100.00)	40 (100.00)	NS
Vigorous & quite	--	60.00 (24)	7.74**
Indoor & outdoor	20 (50.00)	40 (100.00)	6.26**
Proceed from			
Simple to complex	--	40 (100.00)	NS
Familiar to unfamiliar	--	40 (100.00)	NS
Concrete to abstract	--	29 (72.50)	10.14**
Easy to difficult	17 (42.50)	40 (100.00)	7.43**
Known to unknown	--	29 (72.50)	10.14**
Hours of the preschool	40 (100.00)	40 (100.00)	NS
Staff hours	40 (100.00)	40 (100.00)	NS
Promote social & emotional development	40 (100.00)	40 (100.00)	NS
Promote speech & language development	40 (100.00)	40 (100.00)	NS
Activity time	--	40 (100.00)	NS
Organization of parents meetings	40 (100.00)	40 (100.00)	NS
Medium of instruction- Mother tongue	40 (100.00)	36 (90.00)	2.10*
Provision of snacks	40 (100.00)	01 (02.50)	12.64**
Activities as per developmental interest, age& need of children	14 (35.00)	40 (100.00)	8.61**
Promote large & fine muscle development	21 (52.50)	40 (100.00)	5.39**
Promote intellectual development	22 (55.00)	40 (100.00)	5.72**
Promote moral development	12 (30.00)	40 (100.00)	9.66**
Fosters creativity	27 (67.50)	40 (100.00)	4.43**
Comprehensive evaluation	19 (47.50)	40 (100.00)	4.01**
Maximum activities conducted	16 (40.00)	40 (100.00)	3.30**
Link between medium of instruction & dominant language of region	40 (100.00)	29 (72.50)	3.94**
Promote physical development	21 (52.50)	39 (97.50)	5.39**
Working days / week	--	29 (72.50)	10.14**
Daily general health check up is conducted	19 (47.50)	18 (45.00)	0.17 ^{NS}
Field trip or nature walk	--	35 (87.50)	16.36**
Children work with freedom under supervision	40 (100.00)	40 (100.00)	NS
Flexibility in programme	40 (100.00)	40 (100.00)	NS
Activities provide variety of experiences	29 (72.50)	40 (100.00)	3.94**
Child centered programme	19 (47.50)	40 (100.00)	6.71**
First hand experiences	18 (45.00)	40 (100.00)	6.99**
Activity based programme	16 (40.00)	40 (100.00)	7.74**
Multisensorial learning experiences	17 (42.50)	40 (100.00)	7.43**
Programme imbibe cleanliness, independence, discipline, confidence etc in children	--	40 (100.00)	NS
Manage activities by keeping things ready before conducting it	--	40 (100.00)	NS
Informal stress on 3 R's	25 (62.50)	32 (80.00)	1.80 ^{NS}
Play oriented programme	19 (47.50)	35 (87.50)	4.20 ^{NS}
Change place as per activity	--	34 (85.00)	15.05 ^{NS}
Use of teaching aids for every activity	25 (62.50)	34 (85.00)	2.41*
Method of evaluation			
Formal	15 (37.50)	08 (20.00)	1.71 ^{NS}
Informal	25 (62.50)	32 (80.00)	1.80 ^{NS}

Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages **P<0.01level NS -Non-Significant

Table 2: Various activities conducted in selected rural and urban preschools

Various activities	Percentages of preschools based on area (n-80)		Z values
	Rural (40)	Urban (40)	
Indoor play	40 (100.00)	40 (100.00)	NS
Snacks	40 (100.00)	40 (100.00)	NS
Songs	40 (100.00)	40 (100.00)	NS
Prayer	17 (42.50)	40 (100.00)	7.43**
Creative activity	--	40 (100.00)	NS
Outdoor play	--	40 (100.00)	NS
Readiness activity	--	40 (100.00)	NS
Informal talk	18 (45.00)	34 (85.00)	4.13 ^{NS}
Story narration	10 (25.00)	34 (85.00)	6.76**
Health check up	19 (47.50)	18 (45.00)	0.17 ^{NS}
Science experience	--	17 (42.50)	5.38**

Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages **P<0.01level NS -Non-Significant

Table 3: Qualitative parameters of available outdoor play equipments & material in selected rural and urban preschools

Qualitative parameters of available outdoor play equipments & material	Percentages of preschools based on area (n-80)		Z values
	Rural (40)	Urban (40)	
Safe	40 (100.00)	37 (92.50)	1.86 ^{NS}
Durable	40 (100.00)	37 (92.50)	1.86 ^{NS}
Colourful	40 (100.00)	36 (90.00)	2.10*
Attractive	40 (100.00)	37 (92.50)	1.86 ^{NS}
Light in weight	40 (100.00)	37 (92.50)	1.86 ^{NS}
Good quality	40 (100.00)	37 (92.50)	1.86 ^{NS}
Cost effective	--	37 (92.50)	21.44**
Proper installation	--	37 (92.50)	21.44**
Appropriate size & number	--	37 (92.50)	21.44**
Multipurpose	--	25 (62.50)	8.07**
Proper maintenance	--	37 (92.50)	21.44**

Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages **P<0.01level NS- Non-Significant